

Threat perceptions of offshore energy infrastructure in the Baltic Sea: Toward a harmonized approach?

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Abstract—In a context of decarbonization efforts and high geopolitical tensions, offshore energy infrastructure is becoming an increasingly critical contributor to energy mixes, either through production or import capacity. In light of their growing importance, offshore energy infrastructure must be secured accordingly. The security of energy infrastructure in the European Union is a shared competence between the states, the EU and NATO. However, energy security strategies depend on national threat perceptions and risk assessments – running the risk at odds with one another. This paper explores: how the perception of risk and the concept of energy security is assessed in selected EU-Baltic countries, namely Germany, Lithuania and Poland; the interaction between multilateral initiatives on energy security awareness for offshore energy infrastructure and the hypothetical emergence of a harmonized approach.

Index terms— *Energy security, Offshore energy infrastructures, European Union, North-Atlantic Treaty Organization, Threat perception, Risk assessment.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The ongoing transition from fossil-based energy systems to decarbonized ones means that both are currently considered at the same time. This general puzzle applies to offshore energy infrastructure, such as wind energy, oil platforms, or floating energy production units. Geographically speaking, decarbonized energy infrastructure connect a growing number of regions, especially in the North Sea and the Baltic Sea through pipelines, power cables and shared wind farm projects with potential implications for hydrogen production. While the process of interconnection is not new, the bridge between both shores of the Baltic Sea has grown since 2012 as a result of the Baltic Energy Market Interconnection Plan (BEMIP) [1]. In line with climate objectives, offshore energy infrastructure are increasingly contributing to decarbonization efforts in Europe. As stated in the 2020 European Union (EU) strategy on offshore renewable energy, the aim is to install 60GW of offshore wind capacity and 1GW of ocean energy by 2030 and 300GW and 40GW respectively by 2050 [2]. Similarly, the BEMIP framework, aims to install 22.5 GW of offshore renewable capacity by 2030 and 46.8 GW by 2050. [3].

In parallel to the energy transition, Europe is facing the return of neorealist geopolitical dynamics [4], where countries such as –but not exclusively– Russia are trying to expand their regional power through military, diplomatic and economic means. As a reaction, most European countries are trying to maintain a status-quo against the Russian expansionist policy. Since February 2022, offshore infrastructure (particularly in the

energy sector) have been targeted because they are seen as a means of altering the geopolitical balance of power in the Baltic region. This highlights how critical the issue of energy security has become, which is interestingly a concept that does not have a fixed and unified definition in the academic field and among the institutions (EU, NATO, IEA etc.) [5].

Besides being needed for the deployment of (offshore) energy infrastructure, a coordinated response among EU countries to the geopolitical evolutions appears to be a requirement to ensure resilience and to deal with the interconnected consequences of any hostile actions that might target those infrastructures. In such a context, countries developing offshore energy infrastructure in the Baltics face the same challenges – yet diverge so far in their risk perceptions and responses. The construction of LNG terminals in countries bordering the Baltic Sea or the construction of the Nord Stream pipelines are typical case studies of the differences between countries when it comes to their perceptions of risks and their conceptions of security. The first case underlines the willingness to emancipate from Russian gas imports, while the second case reflects the search for more direct and voluminous imports of gas from Russia. [6].

In reaction to Russia’s war of aggression against Ukraine, the European Union launched the REPower EU plan. This plan aims to embargo Russian energy exports (coal, oil and natural gas) while supporting the diversification of fossil-energy supplies and the accelerated deployment of renewable energy capacity. However, energy security had already reemerged as a priority in the last decades, including in NATO circles. This is evidenced by other coordinated responses being prepared well before the Russian aggression (strategic compass, NIS2, etc.). This strategic context paved the way for initiatives aiming to develop a shared vision on risk assessment and to coordinate implementation efforts [7], which notably include the creation in 2012 of the college of defense for energy security (ENSEC-COE) in Vilnius where regular courses are organized in order to raise awareness among the Allies [8].

Within the EU, energy is a shared competence as stipulated in Article 194 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU). While energy mixes and energy supply strategies are still strictly national competences, the EU Commission has influence over solidarity mechanisms, interconnections and incentives for renewable energies. In parallel to EU legislation, NATO competences mainly revolve around energy infrastructures used for military purposes, and those with potential dual uses, since NATO activities in Europe should be able to rely on civilian energy infrastructure [9]. In this sense,

the development of a geographically integrated European energy space seems to follow a multi-level governance dynamic between bottom-up approaches (at communal, and regional levels) and top-down approaches (led by EU institutions) [10].

This paper explores the interaction of multilateral initiatives concerning the energy security awareness for offshore energy infrastructure, the hypothetical emergence of a harmonized approach, and the way the perception of risk and the concept of energy security is assessed in selected EU-countries. It aims to observe and analyze the assumed emergence of a shared vision on energy security using the example of the offshore energy infrastructure in the Baltic region. If so, toward which harmonized approach is it going to? This paper should help to better understand the driving forces behind the harmonization process: does the impulse come from the multilateral institutions (EU or NATO) or from the member states? Depending on the answer to this question, we may be able to find out to what extent this harmonized approach is implemented, from a geographical and political perspective.

The argument will be structured in three parts. A first part describes how energy security issues related to offshore energy infrastructure have been assessed and integrated in the current deployment strategy of selected countries. The second part is dedicated to initiatives undertaken by the EU and NATO in the Baltic region that aim to reinforce energy security of the offshore energy infrastructures and the driving forces behind them. Does the impulse for such initiatives lies in the organizations (EU or NATO) or in one or several selected countries? The last part qualitatively assesses the level of harmonization of the threats perceptions for offshore energy by observing the political and geographical national dynamics that aim to reinforce security of the energy offshore infrastructure.

II. METHODS AND MATERIAL

In this paper, three Baltic countries were selected: namely Germany, Poland and Lithuania. This choice lies in the proven divergences of perceptions of risk to offshore energy infrastructures, notably between Germany and Poland [11]. Lithuania was also chosen because it is assumed that it is representative of the northern Baltic states since it belongs to the Nordic-Baltic Eight (NB8) group, that aims at strengthening cooperation and coordination between eight countries of the Baltic region through high-level meetings held on regular basis to discuss, among others, energy and external affairs issues (neighborhood diplomacy, defense cooperation, etc.).

This paper draws upon qualitative data gathered from primary (official documents, interviews, maps) and secondary sources (academic literature, expert insights). It takes an interdisciplinary approach, using elements of political science and geography -particularly in relation to the theme of regional integration- to identify the dynamics that point to greater integration of specific areas in physical, political or economic terms [12].

III. WHAT RISKS PERCEPTIONS FOR THE DOMESTIC OFFSHORE INFRASTRUCTURES?

Countries consider offshore infrastructure an opportunity to build a more diversified energy import chain, and for pipelines or power interconnectors. With the deployment of renewable

energy (RES), sea spaces are increasingly used to develop energy production capacity (power and hydrogen). The perceived asset here is to be able to build capacity without being constrained by social acceptance issues. Finally, other energy units, such as FRSU or storage capacities, were also added near the coasts as temporary – or mobile – energy infrastructure in order to rapidly respond to the supply shift from the gas import from pipelines to LNG imports.

Figure 1: Undersea gas pipelines in northern Europe, source: European Union, graphic: BBC.

A. Germany

Partially inherited the Cold War and the geographical dynamic of East- and West-Germany, maritime activities and (energy) infrastructure deployment along the domestic coasts are much denser in the North Sea than in the Baltic Sea. This geographic imbalance seems to be reflected at the political-industrial level with a higher number of regular dialogues between the North Sea countries (such as the North Sea Summits) than between countries bordering the Baltic Sea. The densification of overall offshore energy infrastructure along the German coast should however increase according to the national targets, up to 45 GW by 2035 and 70 GW by 2045 [14]. The geographic distribution of future capacities does not seem to be strictly defined beyond 2030. Until 2030, 4,1 GW are planned [15]. The current installed capacities are mostly located in the exclusive economic zones (EEZ), and would support the current trend to connect the Baltic energy units to cross-border projects with the other member states [16].

Germany plans to use the Northern part of its territory as an energy hub for domestic energy production but also as an import gate to the central regions of the country [17]. As a result, energy imports (LNG, electricity and hydrogen) would remain an essential part of the energy supply strategy. In the meantime, the support for RES deployment echoes the federal climate and energy-industrial strategy. Energy industry support – notably for wind and hydrogen – is also considered an important factor to keep economic wealth in the country.

Established security related-activities have been mostly articulated on maritime traffic, with a special attention given to the crisis management and coordination between the federal police, the coast guards, and the German Navy when the two first explicitly delegate to it. [18]. As an exporting country, the economic dimension seems to drive the interest to ensure the unimpeded import and export of freight. Controlling traffic mitigates negative impacts for the domestic economy. In this context, the energy infrastructure can be seen as a risk factor

for maritime movements, particularly in the event of accidents, sabotage or other damage.

The identification of a specific improvement in the physical and cyber protection of offshore infrastructures is considered “relevant for the security of Germany and the other NATO-States” [19]. The issue of the coordination and responsibility between security stakeholders and their responsibilities was raised, particularly with regard to surveillance activities and real-time information on traffic and navigation. One latent question echoes the responsibility and costs-sharing between private actors (mostly companies) and the state actors (federal and regional ministries and the chancellery) for the protection of offshore infrastructure, especially in the EEZ. Whereas energy law essentially relies on principles of private responsibilities, the protection of critical infrastructure seems to be part of the Interior Ministry’s (BMI) competencies, and the Defense Ministry (BMVg) and the Economy and Climate Ministry (BMWK) and the regional ministries of the federal states that have jurisdiction over the relevant coastline. However, these actors have not yet clarified their respective roles, but this is expected to be remedied with the release of a dedicated KRITIS-umbrella law [20].

From the German Navy side, interventions on energy infrastructure are only possible according to Article 35 of the Fundamental Law (*Grundgesetz*) but is not an integrated mission of it [21]. In addition, total protection of the energy infrastructures – in particular the underwater infrastructure - is considered impossible given the size of the maritime zone to be monitored and the current operational resources of the German Navy [22]. However, the BMVg shall have an overview of the critical infrastructure and be able to coordinate relevant parties in the event of intervention.

The efforts made to protect energy infrastructure are therefore based on a reactive posture, with the preparation of crisis management plans and the control of cascading effects at regional and national level, in the event of a disruption to the energy supply within society [23]. The project OWISS – Offshore Wind Energy Protection and Security, led from 2015 to 2018 aimed at developing a regulatory system for prevention and reaction [24]. However, there does not seem to be any mention about a cascade-effect at the European level, especially given the integrated power network.

Figure 2: Power Grid Map, Northern Europe, *ENTSO-E*, 09.2023.

B. Lithuania

Lithuania has heavily relied on the inherited energy dependencies on Russia and Belarus, but also on the LNG imports from other regions that have been encouraged to reduce at least the gas dependencies from Russia and Belarus [25]. In this context, the National Energy Independence Strategy published in 2018 is a set of clear directives to enhance energy security of the country by reducing up to 30% of its energy imports by 2030, by using domestic power, increasing electrification, and better local market integration with the Central European Synchronous Area [26]. Self-sufficiency and the progressive transition away from the Russia/Belarus energy network to the Baltic/Scandinavian and Central European systems are the main objectives.

Electricity production is expected to be fully domestically produced by RES (mostly using wind and solar capacities) by 2050 but will cover 45% of the final consumption needs by 2030. Current plans for 2030 scope 1,4 GW offshore wind capacity, 3,6 GW for onshore wind and 2GW for solar. This latter should be located in the northern part of the country, within the Exclusive Economic Zones (around 30km away from the coastlines). Lithuania is first Baltic state that officially launched two offshore wind parks, which were tendered in 2023 and should be in operation by 2028-2030 [27].

Figure 3: “Restrictions on the design and construction of wind power plants in accordance with national security requirements (basis: Territories of the Republic of Lithuania where the design and construction of wind power plants (tall structures) may be restricted) (approved on 15 February 2016). *Ardynas, Ptpi*, p.41 [cf.70]

Alongside these efforts to promote self-sufficiency, Lithuania seeks more electricity and gas grid integration together with other Baltic States. The phase out of Russian/Belarusian gas and electricity imports geographically isolates the Baltic States. The desynchronization process is underway in Lithuania but should be achieved by 2025. This is prompting the Lithuanian authorities to test the autonomous operation of the national electricity system, separate from Russia, and to test the operation of the integrated electricity systems of the Baltic States. The reason for these tests is that the Lithuanian electricity system is still dependent on Russian frequency control [28].

This shift towards more integrated energy grids is coordinated through the Baltic Energy Market Interconnection Plan (BEMIP), which aims to connect the three countries to other EU Member states [29]. For Lithuania, this translated into an offshore power interconnector, NordBalt (700MW), in operation since 2015 and connecting Sweden and Lithuania for a 30 year-term [30].

Increasing interdependency across the Continental European Network (from Lithuania to Poland) is the main target of the BEMIP. It started with onshore interconnections (Lit-Pol Link – 1000 MW and GIPL for LNG in 2022 [31]) since 2015. The synchronization is expected to start 2025 [32]. So far, the project Harmony Link (700MW), under consideration since 2018, is planned to connect Darbėnai (Northern Lithuania) to Żarnowiec (Poland) and future offshore energy units to increase the integration of the energy network, with the long term option of being connected to a potentially even larger Baltic offshore energy corridor [33]. However, the project seemed to be cancelled in 2021 and has been definitively shifted for an onshore option because of increasing costs [34].

Figure 4: Planned harmony link cable route, harmonylink.eu, 2023

On 21st May 2024, a leak of a draft document from the Russian Ministry of Defense presenting unilateral maritime border changes with Lithuania and Finland raised the question of the existential security of the countries in its national waters and EEZ [35]. Legally speaking, territorial waters correspond to the first line from the coast (12 nautical miles, so 22,2 km) and allows a full control over the maritime activities within this area, while the EEZ allows navigations and legal activities for all the other countries [36]. Since the planned wind farm parks should be installed 30km away from the Lithuanian coastline, as well as the potential Harmony Link would be in the EEZ of Lithuania, Poland and Russia, the development or good-functioning of these infrastructures might be used as leverage for potential maritime border disputes and regional tensions.

The same day the document leaked, the Baltic Council of Ministers and the Baltic Assembly gathered at the conference “Energy Future of the Baltic State: Addressing Regional Challenges Together” under Lithuanian Presidency, and in the face of the leaked information, advocated for a total phase-out Russian energy import (even LNG which are currently not under embargo) and supported further interconnections plans and offshore wind projects. Head of the Seimas Delegation to the Baltic Assembly and President of the Baltic Assembly, Andrius Kupčinskas stated: “This approach further secures the energy security of the region and allows the region **to be better prepared for the unexpected**. However, despite significant progress, many issues remain to be addressed and a number of challenges remain in place [...]” [37]. The Lithuanian Navy is composed of a patrol ships squadron and a MCM ships squadron, which are mostly dispatched to ensure security in the territorial sea and the EEZ; or even over the NordBalt power link as response to the Balticconnector damage in October 2023.

Figure 5: Offshore wind farms in Europe, source: EMODnet, graphic: AFP, 03.2022.

C. Poland

The development of offshore energy infrastructure by Poland has been “modest” compared to other countries’ strategies. Because of the lack of consistency and of long-term thinking, the offshore energy deployment was not planned at an ambitious level in domestic strategies such as the Poland Energy Plan until 2040 (PEP2040) in force since 2021. Several causes can be underlined, such as the difficulties to phase out coal or even gas, the lack of dedicated regulatory framework, or the gap between an EU-vision on the RES deployment versus a “sovereign” conception of the energy system notably by the previous Polish government [38].

Nevertheless, energy security issues have raised a lot of interest in Poland among academics, officials and even civil and military actors for years. With the intensification of the war in Ukraine and the change of government, it seems that political and societal willingness to develop offshore wind energy and to consider it as a means for more energy independence from Russia is emerging [39]. The ongoing processes for the Baltic projects (Baltic 1, 2 and 3), Baltic Power, and the MFW Bałtyk I, II and III, all on the Pomeranian coast, support this trend [40].

Identified offshore infrastructure to protect, in priority, are subsea cables, offshore wind energy units, the FRSU and NNP-related infrastructures (for cooling), which are located mainly in the EEZ. It seems that holistic risk evaluations and intensive threats assessments are ongoing together with defense actors (Ministry of Defense and NATO) since protection of maritime infrastructures is part of the Polish Navy’s mission. This evaluation process will support the elaboration of prevention/reaction plans [41]. Since 2015, national defense is legally enshrined as a key objective of the Polish maritime spatial planning, which might explain why the Polish armed forces are systematically included in the deployment of the offshore wind energy units (a.o. to avoid space usage conflicts), in order to organize surveillance and protection missions [42].

Figure 6: Maritime zones according to the UNCLOS, graphic: Riccardo Pravettoni (2010).

Broadly speaking, the Polish state seems to be more directly implicated in security missions and guarantees for the offshore energy infrastructure, which echoes the country's specificity that most Polish energy companies are more or less state-owned [43]. Therefore, in addition to the use of the EEZ for the deployment of the offshore infrastructure, which may more easily permit state-intervention-systems (military forces, coordinating information centers etc.), the deployment trend of energy offshore infrastructures and their security tend to be a public affair. Naturally, other actors, such as the maritime industry try to also partially influence the way offshore infrastructures will be deployed [44].

If regulations have been specified for the development of offshore wind energy units, plans for interconnections appear less evident [45]. It seems that Poland is also looking for cross-border interconnections, especially with neighbor countries (Germany, Denmark and Lithuania) but does not actively aim at developing broader or further offshore connections – except the planned upgrade SwePol Link (in operation since 2000, 600MW) [46] and the completion of the Baltic pipe project to import gas from Norway through Denmark [47].

IV. EVOLUTION OF EU AND NATO INITIATIVES FOR THE PROTECTION OF THE OFFSHORE ENERGY INFRASTRUCTURE IN THE BALTIC REGION

In 2006, the UNESCO Intergovernmental Oceanic Commission launched an integrative spatial planning process for maritime areas to avoid potential spatial use conflicts, while ensuring a functioning maritime ecosystem. Introduced as an MSP directive in 2014 in the EU, all coastal Member states had to publish their Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) from 2021 for at least a 10-year period. From an EU perspective, the MSP supports the integrated maritime policy of the EU by giving more visibility to possible cross-border cooperation among EU Member states and with third countries in diverse sectors [48]. MSP can include military and security considerations (related-activities and infrastructures) and as well integrate marine infrastructures that are considered critical for national safety and security (pipelines, transmission cables, etc.) [49]. The integration of such infrastructures in the MSP remains national. At the initiative of HELCOM and VASAB [50] or the Baltic SCOPE group [51], the search for a supranational perspective to ensure security is mentioned - but without fundamentally harmonizing the national security and defense interests of the countries involved, such as the energy infrastructures [52].

Energy interconnection among countries of the Baltic Sea region is seen as a milestone and it is structured at the EU-level as shown by a dedicated strategy published in 2012 [53]. Since 2008 a high-level Group has been constituted to implement a

Baltic Energy Market Interconnection Plan (BEMIP) that focuses on projects of common interest (cross-border and national). The integration of the Baltic States' electricity network with the Nordic countries and continental European network through Poland has been organized since 2019 [54]. A commitment declaration for offshore development in the Baltic Sea region was signed in 2020 to echo the EU Offshore Renewable Energy strategy [55]. Among other priorities, the BEMIP offshore wind WG will deepen the cooperation and coordination with the MSP WGs, the North Seas Energy Cooperation (NSEC) [56] and the NCA Platform [57]. Following the Marienberg declaration in July 2022 on energy security in the Baltic Sea, participating nations signed a non-binding agreement on goals for future offshore renewable generation in the region as a means to reduce EU dependency on fossil fuel [58]. Although offshore wind energy was identified as a means for the security of the energy supply by reducing the dependency on Russia, the securitization of the offshore energy infrastructures protection or risks assessment are not mentioned in those documents.

Yet the energy sector belongs to the list of essential services (commission delegated regulation 2023/2450) [59] and is also part of a specific directive on the resilience of critical entities (2022/2557). This directive aims at giving a framework to the Member states to identify risks and secure critical infrastructure, whose disruption or destruction would have a significant cross-border impact on at least two Member states [60]. Legally, risk assessment and reaction plans remain a national competence, while a state's obligation towards the EU Commission is to ensure the prevention of incident with negative European impacts and the capability to recover the situation as soon as possible.

Figure 7: Schematic regional context between 2025 and 2050 (non-exhaustive), Lithuania energy system transformation to 2050, EPSOG, DNV, 07.2023

Article 3 of the NATO Treaty stipulates that each Parties must collectively and individually ensure their “capacity to resist armed attack” [61]. The article echoes the concept of resilience developed in 2016 [62] and re-committed in 2021 [63], which considers the protection and good functioning of the civilian infrastructure, network and supply, on which military activities depend. Security of energy supply, as well as the security of functioning energy infrastructures (ex: transmission and transport infrastructures) have thus been issued within NATO, more specifically within the Resilience committee (Energy Planning Group – EPG) and the Energy Security Centre of Excellence (ENSEC-CoE), whose objective is to raise awareness

and be a knowledge hub on these issues. A table-top exercise focused on the maritime and offshore energy installations Baltic region “Coherent Resilience 2023 Baltic” was also organized in cooperation with the EU JRC and US NPS [64].

In January 2023, the President of the European Commission and the Secretary General of NATO launched a dedicated NATO-EU Task Force on the resilience of critical infrastructure. The EU and NATO worked together to conceive and adapt to the geopolitical context “parallel and coordinated assessments, and to take action to mitigate potential vulnerabilities” [65]. Since “[...] full protection is generally not possible [...] cooperation at regional and international level, including through international organizations, is indispensable” [65, p.3]. Among the first key recommendations of the EU-NATO task force in June 2023 that should be implemented by the EU-NATO Structured Dialog on Resilience, one suggested that more coordination should take place between the EU Critical Entities Resilience Group and Politico Military Group, and the NATO’s Resilience Committee, while another called for exploring specific solutions for the maritime domain, notably by enhancing the maritime situational awareness [65, p.9]. A specific critical undersea infrastructure coordination cell was set up after the sabotage of the Nord Stream pipeline in order to share best-practice and coordinate efforts among Allies [66].

V. WHAT LEVEL OF HARMONIZATION OF THE THREAT PERCEPTION? TOWARD A COMMON SECURITIZATION APPROACH?

The energy infrastructure and networks in the Baltic Sea have been increasingly integrated. This dynamic has been structured within several multilateral organizations and initiatives, and was supported by the EU. The main objective of this process has been to create synergies and enhance energy flow efficiency among the participating countries, while also de-isolating them from inherited energy networks. The development of decarbonized energy sources has been heavily supported by the EU as a path to decarbonization, while NATO has progressively focused on the resilience and security of energy supply and infrastructure.

Geopolitical developments in the region have raised political and institutional commitments at every level – nationally, multilaterally, EU and NATO – and led to a common approach regarding energy security. First, every energy infrastructure is now systematically registered as critical infrastructure, considering the serious negative impact their malfunctioning may have on society. Second, Russia’s aggression war on Ukraine led to a common strategy among states of the Baltic Sea on the need to reduce energy dependence on Russia by coordinating the LNG-supply chains and deploying offshore wind energy. Third, there is an increasing awareness that energy infrastructures (offshore, coastal and subsea) can be targeted and used as geopolitical leverage. If this infrastructure is not fully protected, it increases the need for multilateral cooperation and coordination.

In this context, the EU and NATO provide an efficient framework for cooperation and coordination in line with their competences and guidance tools. Nevertheless, the risk assessments and the preventive/reactive plans remain strictly national. Through multilateral discussions and frameworks, the

countries share their views, positions and practices, which tend to give an overall orientation for the region. The Marienborg Declaration of July 2022 [67] and the conference in May 2024 “Energy Future of the Baltic States: Addressing Regional Challenges Together” that gathered the Baltic Council of Ministers and the Baltic Assembly illustrate this multilateral dynamic [68].

However, the intensity of the threat perceptions as well as state commitment to prevent negative impacts can vary. In the case of Germany, key commitments were made to ensure free shipping routes and a rapid restoration of traffic from an incident through reactive crisis management plans. There is still a lack of clarity among the relevant parties regarding the prevention of offshore energy and subsea infrastructure risks, including considerations of responsibility and cost allocation. In the meantime, it is not included in the German Navy’s mission scope. Lithuanian assessments towards the offshore energy infrastructure is driven by the search for a full energy independence from Russia, as maritime borders are used as geopolitical leverage by Moscow. This tends to create an existential threat environment which leads to political commitments focusing on a high level of resilience, with or without offshore energy capacities. Poland seems to have a third assessment that emphasizes preventive actions to avoid incidents (especially with a geopolitical dimension) translating into more state commitment as security provider within its EEZ.

If the three cases showed the same willingness to include and even extend the EU and NATO dimensions on these issues, the underlying motivations might somehow vary. In the case of Lithuania, it seems to echo the need for strengthening the protection means in an unsecured environment. Poland might see organizations such as NATO and the EU as a way to structure and consolidate strategies to protect offshore infrastructure. Finally, Germany seems to use NATO and the EU as a way to mutualize efforts to secure offshore energy infrastructure.

Beside the various national driving forces and perceptions, the question of the responsibility tends to rely on national assessments. The German and Polish cases highlight these national differences: a separation of responsibilities between the private and public actors on security activities in Germany, while Poland organizes these activities with a higher involvement of the state. For EU and NATO, states must ensure their effort to guarantee the good functioning of the energy infrastructure, especially when it comes to cross-border or interconnected networks. The EU-NATO task force presented in June 2023 the inclusion of the energy infrastructures as critical entities for the societies and gave the states responsibility over them, even if they are owned or operated by private actors [65 p.3-4]. This might help harmonization on this matter.

One could summarize that questions: *Why* [protecting the offshore energy infrastructures]? *What* [to protect exactly]? and *How* [to protect them]? have been harmonized among the countries of the Baltic Sea. Accordingly to the national dimension of the threat assessments, the question: [protecting] *From what* [exactly]? seems to be the most difficult to answer –especially in a harmonized way-, since it relies on uncertain factors that must be identified. Yet, the degree of preparation regarding this last question might give the strongest level of resilience to the states and the interconnected areas. Ensuring a sufficient level

of resilience towards offshore energy infrastructure legitimates political influence in energy, defense, and security policy at EU and NATO levels. This reaffirms strategic leadership in light of the regional geopolitical tensions [69].

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